

FROM SPEECH TO ACTION: EXPLORING HATE SPEECH ORIGINS, IMPACT, AND INTERVENTIONS FROM MULTIDISCIPLINARY PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

Hate speech is an intricate and multifaceted reality that poses significant risks to democratic nations. Its consequences extend far beyond mere words, leading to physical harm, social isolation, heightened tension, increased anxiety, and depression, among other detrimental effects. Understanding the origins, patterns, and impact of hate speech is crucial for developing effective interventions and policies to combat it. This is particularly relevant in today's context, where the proliferation of social media platforms has facilitated the rapid dissemination and amplification of hate speech.

This research paper aims to explore hate speech from a multi-disciplinary perspective, encompassing psychological, social, legal, and technological dimensions. The paper also explores the origins and limitations of hate speech laws in India, highlighting the challenges of defining it within the existing legal framework. It adopts a secondary research approach, drawing upon existing literature and the insights of scholars who have extensively studied hate speech in India. By incorporating diverse perspectives, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

Additionally, the paper also mentions our project which focuses on analyzing hate speech reporting in India using data-driven methods. The project uses Latent Dirichlet Allocation for topic modeling, revealing underlying themes. Overall, it contributes to a comprehensive understanding of hate speech reporting and can guide future interventions and policies for a safer online environment.

Note: *This is a working paper, the interviews with scholars are currently ongoing and the text will be updated soon accordingly.*

BACKGROUND

Hate speech is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon that has far-reaching and dangerous consequences in democratic societies. Hate speech refers to speech, conduct, writing, or expression that offends, threatens, or incites violence or discrimination against individuals or groups based on attributes such as race, ethnicity, religion, gender, sexual orientation, disability, or nationality. It can include derogatory language, slurs, insults, and discriminatory remarks that are intended to degrade, demean, or harm individuals or communities (United Nations).

The effects of hate speech can be severe and include physical harm, social isolation, an increase in tension, anxiety, and depression, among other things. Hate speech is an assault on inclusiveness, diversity, and human rights in addition to harming individuals and having the potential to provoke violence. It erodes shared values and social cohesion, putting an end to development, peace, and the realisation of everyone's human rights (Council of Europe, 2022).

Hate speech creates dangerous divisions within society, undermines participation and inclusion, and poses a threat to democracy. The targets of hate speech are often marginalised, silenced, and excluded from public discourse, and history has shown that hate speech has been deliberately used to mobilise groups against each other, leading to violent escalation, hate crimes, wars, and even genocides (Council of Europe, 2022).

Hate speech also restricts the ability of targeted individuals to freely express their ideas, voice their concerns, and be adequately represented. It can be used to intimidate or silence minority groups, human rights defenders, NGO representatives, politicians, journalists, and other media actors reporting on matters of public interest. The chilling effect of hate speech on journalists and media professionals has been documented in various reports, highlighting how investigations

and reporting can make them the target of severe propaganda and hate speech campaigns, particularly in the online environment. The misuse or threatened use of hate speech laws and other types of legislation can also effectively silence contributions to the public debate (Council of Europe, 2022).

IMPORTANCE OF STUDYING HATE SPEECH

Given the harmful effects of hate speech, understanding its origins, patterns, and impact is essential for creating effective interventions and policies to combat it. This is particularly important in today's context, where the rise of social media platforms has made it easier than ever for hate speech to spread and gain momentum. Furthermore, hate speech can be a precursor to more serious forms of violence, making it a critical issue for public safety and national security. By studying hate speech, we can develop a better understanding of how to prevent it and mitigate its effects.

Therefore, the aim of this research paper on hate speech is to investigate the definition, prevalence and impact of hate speech in different parts of the world, and to analyse the roadblocks that limit the states and society from combatting this phenomenon. Through the examination of these notions, this paper seeks to identify common themes, differences, and challenges associated with hate speech in diverse cultural, social, and political contexts.

By exploring the experiences of different countries and communities, this paper aims to deepen our understanding of the causes and consequences of hate speech, and to identify effective strategies for prevention, education, and regulation. Specifically, the paper will examine the impact of hate speech on marginalized groups such as ethnic and religious minorities, LGBTQ+ communities, and women, and will highlight the ways in which hate speech can contribute to discrimination, violence, and human rights violations.

Moreover, the paper also discusses our initiative, which centers on examining hate speech reporting in India through data-driven approaches. Employing Latent Dirichlet Allocation for topic modeling, the project uncovers fundamental themes. In essence, it enhances our grasp of hate speech reporting and has the potential to inform future actions and policies to foster a safer online space.

Overall, the purpose of this research paper is to contribute to the ongoing discourse on hate speech, and to provide insights and recommendations for policymakers, activists, and educators seeking to create a more inclusive, respectful, and tolerant society.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this research paper is to explore the phenomenon of hate speech from a multi-disciplinary perspective, examining its psychological, social, legal, and technological dimensions.

To achieve our goal, we aim to learn findings from secondary research, drawing from existing literature and insights of scholars who have extensively worked on this area in India. This approach will provide a comprehensive understanding of the topic and enrich our study with diverse perspectives. Some of the key research questions that will be addressed in this paper include:

- What is the definition of hate speech, and how has it evolved over time?
- How does hate speech impact social cohesion in India?
- What are the psychological and social effects of hate speech on individuals and communities?
- What legal frameworks and policies exist to address hate speech, and how effective are they in practice?
- How has the rise of social media platforms contributed to the spread of hate speech, and what are the challenges of regulating speech online?

- How can education and awareness be used to combat hate speech and promote tolerance?
- How does analysing hate speech reporting in India using data-driven methods contribute to a safer online environment?

By answering these questions, this research paper seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of hate speech and its implications for society.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Hate Speech

Source of Definition	Overview
United Nations' International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights	Any advocacy of national, racial or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility, or violence. - Article 20(2) of the ICCPR (OHCHR).
European Court of Human Rights	The use of expressions which spread, incite, promote, or justify hatred based on intolerance. - Various judgments (European Court of Human Rights, 2023).
Committee of Ministers from Council of Europe	All types of expression that incite, promote, spread, or justify violence, hatred, or discrimination against a person or group of persons, or that denigrates them, by reason of their real or attributed personal characteristics or status such as 'race,' colour, language, religion, nationality, national or ethnic origin, age, disability, sex, gender identity, and sexual orientation (Council of Europe).
European Union	All conduct that publicly incites to violence or hatred, including using certain means of communication, such as the Internet (European Commission Against Racism and Intolerance).

Source of Definition	Overview
Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE)	Any kind of communication in speech, writing, or behaviour that attacks or uses pejorative or discriminatory language with reference to a person or a group on the basis of who they are, in other words, based on their religion, ethnicity, nationality, race, color, descent, gender, or other identity factor.
United Kingdom	Any threatening, abusive, or insulting words or behaviour that is likely to stir up hatred against a particular individual or group based on their identity, including race, religion, sexual orientation, or disability. - Public Order Act 1986 and Criminal Justice Act 1994 (Public Order Act 1986; Criminal Justice and Public Order Act 1994).
Canada	Any expression that is likely to expose a person or group to hatred or contempt. Hate speech is prohibited if it promotes genocide or incites hatred against an identifiable group based on race, religion, national or ethnic origin, colour, sex, sexual orientation, gender identity or expression, or mental or physical disability. - Criminal Code (Justitia, 2020).
Germany	The German Criminal Code (Section 130) addresses incitement of masses. It states that anyone who incites hatred against a national, racial, religious, or ethnic group, or violates the human dignity of others based on their belonging to such groups, can face imprisonment for three months to five years. Additionally, disseminating or making available material that promotes hatred, violence, or insults against these groups, particularly to minors, can result in imprisonment for up to three years or a fine. The Network Enforcement Act complements these provisions by requiring social network providers to promptly remove or block access to unlawful content, including hate speech (Justitia, 2020).

Source of Definition	Overview
Australia	Any expression that is likely to offend, insult, humiliate, or intimidate a person or group based on their race, religion, national origin, or other characteristic. - Racial Discrimination Act 1975 and Criminal Code Act 1995 (RACIAL DISCRIMINATION ACT 1975 - SECT 18C; Justitia, 2020).

HISTORY OF HATE SPEECH

Hate speech has a long and complex history that spans across different cultures and countries. From ancient times to today, there have been numerous examples of hate speech that have led to discrimination, violence, and even genocide. Ancient societies used hate speech to justify the oppression of marginalized groups, such as slaves (Konstan, 2007) and women (Seitkasimova, 2020). In medieval Europe, religious minorities such as Jews (Encyclopedia Britannica) and Muslims (Constable, 2009) were often targets of hate speech that led to violence and discrimination. In the 20th century, the rise of totalitarian regimes in Europe, such as Nazi Germany (Rosenfeld, 2001) and Soviet Russia, led to the use of hate speech as a tool of political control and propaganda.

In the United States, hate speech has been used to dehumanize and oppress marginalized groups throughout history, particularly in relation to race and ethnicity. For example, during the Civil Rights Movement of the 1960s, segregationists used hate speech to oppose equal rights for African Americans (American Experience, 2018). More recently, the rise of the internet and social media has made it easier for hate groups to spread their message and target vulnerable communities, leading to a surge in hate speech online (OHCHR).

In other developed countries, hate speech has also been a problem. For example, in Europe, there have been numerous instances of hate speech targeting immigrants, Jews, Muslims, and other minorities. In 2011, a Norwegian far-right extremist carried out a mass shooting that

targeted a youth camp and a government building, killing 77 people. The attacker had posted numerous hate-filled comments online before the attack (Muhammad, n.d.). In the aftermath of World War II, many European countries introduced laws and regulations that aimed to curtail hate speech, recognizing the devastating impact it had had on their societies. However, hate speech has remained a persistent issue in many parts of Europe, particularly in relation to migration and Islamophobia (Islamophobia in Europe, 2018).

In developing countries, hate speech has also been a significant problem, often fuelled by ethnic, religious, or political divisions and has often been used as a tool to mobilize and incite violence against minority groups.

In Sri Lanka, for example, hate speech has played a major role in the long-standing conflict between the majority Sinhalese population and the Tamil minority (The New Indian Express, 2016) (Amarasinghe, 2023). Similarly, in Myanmar, hate speech has been used to fuel violence and discrimination against the Rohingya Muslim minority (United States Holocaust Memorial Museum, n.d.).

In Africa, hate speech has been a major issue in the context of ethnic and political conflict. In Rwanda in the 1990s, hate speech played a major role in the genocide of Tutsi people by Hutu extremists, who used radio broadcasts and other media to dehumanize and demonize their victims (Ndahiro, 2019). In South Africa, hate speech has been a persistent issue in the context of the country's complex history of racial segregation and discrimination, with both black and white South Africans using hate speech to target each other (Houston, 2022).

In India, hate speech has been a major issue in the context of the country's complex caste system, which divides people into hierarchical groups based on their birth. Dalits, who are at the bottom of the caste hierarchy, have long faced discrimination and violence, often fuelled by hate speech from higher-caste individuals and groups (The Norwegian Human Rights Fund). Similarly, members of the country's Muslim

minority have been targeted by hate speech and violence from Hindu nationalist groups, who seek to promote a Hindu-only vision of India (Al Jazeera).

Despite the complexity and diversity of the history of hate speech in different countries, there are some common threads that run through many of these contexts. Hate speech often arises in the context of social and political conflict and is used as a tool to mobilize and incite violence against minority groups. It is often linked to broader systems of discrimination and marginalization, such as racism, sexism, and homophobia. Overall, the history of hate speech is a complex and troubling one, with numerous examples from both developed and developing countries. While some countries have laws and regulations to combat hate speech, it remains a significant challenge to promote tolerance and respect for diversity.

HATE SPEECH LAWS IN VARIOUS COUNTRIES

Developing Nations

Country Name	Laws
Brazil	Brazilian criminal code has laws that prevent racism, discrimination, and the loss of dignity of people. Article 140 penalises insulting a person’s dignity or decorum on the basis of race, colour, ethnicity, religion, origin or the condition of an elderly person or person with a disability. Article 20 (1) penalises the practice and incitement of discrimination or prejudice against any race, colour, ethnicity, religion, or national origin (Justitia, 2020).
South Africa	Article 16 (1) of the South African Constitution guarantees the right to freedom of expression; however, this does not include propaganda for war, incitement of violence, and advocacy of hatred, especially if that incites harm. In 2016, the South African government introduced the Prevention and Combating of Hate Crimes and Hate Speech Bill which was revised again in 2018. The 2018 Bill aims to prevent and combat offences of hate crime and hate speech (Justitia, 2020).

Country Name	Laws
Bangladesh	Article 153A of the Criminal Code of Bangladesh legally punishes the promotion of enmity or hatred between different citizens and classes of Bangladesh. Section 28 of the Digital Security Act, 2018 prohibits the publication and broadcast of information that hampers religious sentiments or values in any website or in electronic format. Any person who intentionally uploads such content is punishable under this article (Justitia, 2020).
Argentina	Article 3 under the Law 23.592 Discriminatory Acts prohibits any person from carrying out propaganda and joining organisations that carry out such propaganda against that consider one race or group superior and promote discrimination based on religion, race, ethnic origin, or colour. The same penalty is also applicable to those who encourage or incite hatred and persecution against such groups. Article 25(c) under Law 26.522 Audiovisual Communication prohibits the abuse of Information and Communication Technology for acts motivated by xenophobia, racism and other types of hatred and intolerance (Justitia, 2020).
Kenya	Kenyan Penal Code, Section 77(3)(e) punishes any person who acts or conspires with subversive intentions, and in this context, subversive intentions promote hatred or enmity between different communities and races in Kenya. Article 13 of the National Cohesion and Integration Act, 2008 deals with hate speech; any person who contributes to the incitement of ethnic hatred in any way is liable for punishment. Kenya also has a National Action Plan against hate speech Githinji, 2021; Justitia, 2020).

Developed Nations

Country Name	Laws
US	Does not have any hate speech laws as it infringes on the freedom of speech.
UK	In the United Kingdom, legislation has been established to address racial and religious hatred, aiming to prevent the use of threatening, abusive, or insulting words, behaviour, or written material that may incite hatred. Part III of the

Country Name	Laws
	<p>legislation focuses on racial hatred. The subsections address the areas under which an individual can be held liable. Part 3A deals with hatred against individuals based on religious grounds (Justitia, 2020).</p>
<p>Canada</p>	<p>In Canada, there are laws that address hate speech and the promotion of hatred against identifiable and minority groups. Under Article 319(1), it is an offense to publicly communicate statements that incite hatred, likely leading to a breach of the peace. Article 319(2) deals with the wilful promotion of hatred against identifiable groups, excluding private conversations. Article 319(2.1) specifically targets the wilful promotion of antisemitism by downplaying, denying, or condoning the Holocaust. There are several provisions made for defences as well (Legislative Services Branch, 2023).</p>
<p>France</p>	<p>France has laws that prohibit threats made against individuals due to their ethnicity, nationality, race, religion, or sexual orientation with imprisonment or fine. The Law of 29 July 1881 on the Freedom of the Press addresses the support and provocation of crimes or misdemeanours. Non-public insults targeting individuals or groups based on origin, ethnicity, nationality, race, religion, sex, sexual orientation, gender identity, or disability is punished under Article R625-8-1 and non-public provocation to discrimination under Article R625-7 (Justitia, 2020).</p>
<p>Switzerland</p>	<p>Article 261 targets discrimination and incitement to hatred. The Swiss Criminal Code includes provisions that prohibit the incitement of hatred or discrimination based on race, ethnicity, or religion. Specifically, Article 261bis criminalizes public incitement to racial hatred or discrimination, with penalties ranging from fines to imprisonment. This law aims to prevent the spread of hateful ideas and promote a society that values diversity, tolerance, and respect (Justitia, 2020).</p>

THE ORIGINS AND CHALLENGES OF HATE SPEECH LAWS IN INDIA

The origin of hate speech laws in India can be traced back to the British colonial era. According to Rajeev Dhavan (2007), the British initially introduced these provisions to maintain security and stability in their colonial territories. The focus was on preventing communal tension, regardless of who was right or wrong. Asad Ali Ahmed (2009) further argues that implementing hate speech laws by the British helped legitimise their presence in India. By positioning themselves as neutral arbiters of culture and conflict, the British sought to reshape their role from colonial occupiers to guardians of social order. However, this justification is based on the "especially sensitive religious sensibilities" of Indian colonial subjects, which paradoxically led to the very situation that was used to validate the existence of such laws. The introduction of hate speech laws created a legal framework in which claims could be made based on emotional states, cultivating a legal vocabulary centred around hurt sentiments.

Lawrence Liang (2012) points out that attempts to regulate and address wounded attachments and religious passions through law may unintentionally reinforce and perpetuate them. In other words, creating a legal category of hatred, with its boundaries and content defined by the law, may inadvertently contribute to the proliferation of hate speech. He argues that the continued presence of the British was justified by the notion of "emotionally excitable subjects" requiring "a rational and neutral arbiter" to govern and control their relationships. This notion of a neutral arbiter has been passed on to the judiciary, which Liang criticises. He argues that the judiciary is not immune to the politics of communal hatred. Therefore, when hate speech cases are adjudicated, the judicial process itself may become a platform for the production of hate speech.

In this regard, one can look at *Joseph Bain D'Souza v Bal Thackeray*, in which the Court's endorsement of a broad definition of "Muslims

indulging in anti-national activities" seemed to legitimise rather than prohibit hatred. The Court further argued that readers are not likely to develop ill will towards all Muslims but only those Muslims who engage in anti-national activities. The case of *Joseph Bain D'Souza v Bal Thackeray* is a cautionary example that challenges the traditional British perspective on the role of courts in hate speech cases. (Jamia Millia Islamia, 2012). According to this perspective, the courts were seen as pervasive and omniscient, with the state and its courts positioned as an external sovereign entity standing above and outside society. This view clearly distinguished between the state and society in traditional British jurisprudence. However, the case of *Joseph Bain D'Souza v Bal Thackeray* reveals the potential flaws in this conception of the courts. By highlighting the potential appropriation of hate speech laws to serve certain interests, the case raises questions about the neutrality and effectiveness of the courts in addressing hate speech cases. It implies that the courts' role in promoting communal harmony may be compromised when they become entangled in partisan agendas. (Jamia Millia Islamia, 2012).

As we have seen, Indian hate speech laws originated in the colonial era. However, it is important to note that India's legal framework does not have a specific statute that directly addresses hate speech, nor does it provide a precise definition for it. However, there are provisions within the Indian Penal Code (IPC) that can be utilised to charge individuals engaging in hate speech. Furthermore, the Representation of Peoples Act, 1951, and the Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribe (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989 can also be extended to address hate speech in certain contexts. In addition to these specific laws, the state has the authority under the Criminal Procedure Code to curb hate speech, such as banning certain forms of speech or representation that incite hatred or communal tensions.

IPC sections 153A, 153B, 295, 295A, 298, 505(1) and 505(2) which can be understood to have elements of hate speech laws. Sections 153A

and 153B address acts promoting enmity between different religious, racial, or linguistic groups while prohibiting acts detrimental to national harmony. Sections 295 and 295A deal with actions insulting religious beliefs and causing religious disharmony. Section 298 covers deliberate insults to religious feelings, and Sections 505(1) and 505(2) target acts intended to incite hatred and provoke public disturbances, respectively, in other words, they deal with public mischief. (Maniyar & Maniyar, 2022)

There is a need for a separate understanding of hate speech due to the limitations of existing penal provisions rooted in India's colonial past. The current legal framework primarily focuses on acts detrimental to harmony between different groups rather than addressing the devaluation and dehumanisation of specific communities through vile insults. The Supreme Court's ruling in the Bilal Ahmed Kaloo v State of Andhra Pradesh case further illustrates that merely hurting religious sentiments may not amount to crimes under the relevant sections of IPC, highlighting the need for a more nuanced approach to hate speech. (Maniyar & Maniyar, 2022)

Hate speech is not just about promoting enmity; it gradually erodes the confidence and dignity of the targeted community. Therefore, a separate approach is necessary to deal with hate speech effectively. The strength of a Hate Speech Law can be derived from the restrictions on the violent actions that are incited based on hate speech, discrimination that is caused against a group of people, and the curtailment of equality and dignity that results.

In this regard, three main issues have to be dealt with: the inadequacy of the current legal framework for dealing with hate speech, the compatibility of hate speech restrictions with constitutional rights, and the importance of meaningful conversations and awareness as outcomes of a hate speech law. If implemented, the impact of a hate speech law may be more significant in terms of initiating conversations and raising awareness rather than achieving convictions. This implies

that the primary goal of a hate speech law should be to stimulate public dialogue and promote a culture of tolerance rather than solely focusing on legal consequences. It is also essential to discuss the definition and determination of what constitutes hate speech, as this is essential for establishing the basis for imposing restrictions on such speech. Clearly defining hate speech would enable a more effective and targeted approach to addressing and curbing its harmful effects. (Maniyar & Maniyar, 2022).

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL EFFECTS OF HATE SPEECH

Hate speech disproportionately affects vulnerable groups and communities, acting as a unique burden that can cause significant suffering for certain populations, while others remain ignorant or indifferent to its impact. It leads to both psychological and physical harm and has far-reaching consequences for a wide range of minority and indigenous groups.

In an article named "Defining and diminishing hate speech" (2014), it is argued that the increasing prevalence of hate speech has raised concerns across various communities due to its potential to cause significant harm in multiple ways. Directly impacting its targets, hate speech instils fear, offends, humiliates, and belittles individuals. Consequently, it often silences them by instilling a sense of fear. Additionally, hate speech can indirectly, but still profoundly, harm by inciting or fostering hostility between different groups of people. This progression from hatred to discrimination and dehumanization is a dangerous path that can ultimately lead to acts of violence.

In another 2016 article titled "Evidencing the Harms of Hate Speech," the authors conducted a study to investigate the negative consequences associated with hate speech. The study involved interviewing individuals who had experienced hate speech firsthand. The researchers found that the harms reported by the interviewees

encompassed various aspects, including the ability to influence others to believe in negative stereotypes, the normalization of racism in the surrounding environment, and the tendency of listeners to imitate the hateful behaviour. Additionally, the harms included subordination, silencing, fear, victimization, emotional distress, restrictions on freedom, decreased self-esteem, the perpetuation of power imbalances, and the violation of human dignity.

It is important to note that not every instance of hate speech resulted in all these harms, and it was not necessary to demonstrate that harms always occurred in order to support the argument that hate speech is capable of inflicting these negative consequences. Some interviewees mentioned that a person concerned could choose to walk away or disregard the incident as ineffective. However, these exceptions did not undermine the overall argument regarding the potential harms caused by hate speech.

The study also highlighted that public hate speech is often perceived as an attack on a person's worth and dignity. One significant example of widely circulated messages that fuel hatred against a particular group is the dissemination of negative stereotypes through the media. The interviewees were aware of these negative stereotypes propagated in the media and experienced extensive harm as a result. Their strong statements served as evidence that widely disseminated negative stereotypes can indeed inflict the described harms.

Furthermore, the study emphasized that these harms are often enduring and not transient. Racist slurs, for instance, leave a lasting impact and are not easily forgotten, especially when the target encounters another attack or encounters hate speech about their community.

The data from the study strongly support the argument put forth by Delgado (1993) that hate speech can cause significant harm, irrespective of the presence of "fighting words" or an immediate risk of

public disorder. Parekh (2012) similarly argues against the common mistake of defining hate speech solely as speech likely to incite public disorder. The harms resulting from hate speech that fall outside these narrow categories should not be dismissed as insignificant. They have a profound impact on the targets, hindering their full participation in society. The isolation, silencing, and denial of identity experienced by some interviewees underscore the severity of these harms and reveal a contradiction between the lived experiences of the targets and the inclusive and egalitarian goals embedded in hate speech laws.

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN THE SPREAD OF HATE SPEECH

Serving as the central hub for our personal and public activities, the digital realm has enabled unrestricted and anonymous interactions that were unimaginable in the past. Unlike the physical world, the internet has also become a vehicle for the rapid spread and intensification of false information and hate, reaching a much larger audience than ever before.

The study “Spread of hate speech in online social media” (2019) asserted that the current online platforms face numerous issues, with hate speech being the most prominent one. The researchers conducted a pioneering study that examined the flow and dynamics of posts generated by both hateful and non-hateful users on Gab (gab.com), utilizing a vast dataset of 341,000 users and 21 million posts. Their findings established that hateful content diffuses further, reaches a wider audience, and spreads faster compared to non-hateful content. Additionally, a closer analysis of the profiles and networks of hateful and non-hateful users revealed that the former tend to be more influential, popular, and cohesive. Hence, their research delves into the intriguing aspects of how hateful users spread their content and enhances our comprehension of hate speech in the online realm.

The article from the Council on Foreign Relations (CFR) titled "Hate Speech on Social Media: Global Comparisons" (2019) provided a comprehensive overview of the issue of hate speech on social media platforms worldwide. The article stated that the increasing number of attacks targeting immigrants and minority groups has raised concerns about the link between inflammatory online speech and real-world violence. The role of corporations and governments in regulating speech has also come under scrutiny. Hate crimes around the world often align with shifts in the political climate, and social media platforms can amplify discord.

The article argued that the dissemination of rumours and hate speech online has contributed to violent acts, including lynchings and ethnic cleansing, reported on various continents. With a significant portion of the global population using social media, individuals with racist, misogynistic, or homophobic tendencies can find like-minded communities that reinforce their views and encourage violence. Additionally, social media provides a platform for violent actors to publicize their actions.

The regulation of online hate speech poses a significant challenge in balancing the protection of freedom of speech and curbing harmful content. In their article titled "Hate speech regulation on social media: A contemporary challenge," (2020) the authors explore this issue, acknowledging the transformative power of the Internet while highlighting the amplification of hate speech on social media platforms. They emphasise the need for a shared understanding of the importance of freedom of speech and the complexities surrounding hate speech regulation.

Defining Hate Speech and Its Justifications: Establishing a universally accepted definition of hate speech is difficult due to diverse interpretations. The authors discuss two primary justifications for prohibiting hate speech, the incitement to harm principle and the degrading of groups principle. While incitement to violence against

specific groups is widely outlawed, the interpretation and application of freedom of speech and hate speech remain areas of disagreement.

Challenges in Regulating Online Hate Speech: The unique nature of social media platforms presents challenges for effective hate speech regulation. The speed and volume of content, coupled with the absence of editorial oversight, make it difficult to regulate hate speech adequately. The authors note the suggestion of assigning responsibility to social media platforms for implementing efficient complaint mechanisms and removing unlawful speech. However, this approach carries the risk of unintended consequences, such as stifling online expression or inadvertently removing lawful speech.

Regulatory Landscape in Major Jurisdictions: The authors analyse hate speech regulation in four major jurisdictions. The United States, guided by the First Amendment, protects freedom of speech but allows private actors like social media platforms to impose their own restrictions. The United Kingdom employs criminal prohibitions on hate speech both online and in print. The European Union has issued a Code of Conduct on Countering Illegal Content Online, while Germany's Network Enforcement Law imposes obligations on social media platforms to establish effective complaint management mechanisms.

Strategies to Combat Online Hate Speech: The article by Alexandra A. Siegel titled "Online Hate Speech" (2020) explores strategies to combat hate speech, focusing on content moderation and counter-speech. Content moderation involves removing accounts or communities that violate platform rules, but its effectiveness is mixed. Studies show both a reduction in hate speech on platforms like Reddit and Twitter and migration of banned users to alternative platforms. Concerns arise regarding biased implementation, limited adaptation to local contexts, and unintended consequences.

Counter-speech campaigns, offline and online, have been employed to combat hate speech and discrimination. Research suggests that

counter-speech interventions, particularly when delivered by high-status or influential individuals, can reduce instances of hate speech. However, further research is needed to understand the most effective types of counter-speech in diverse contexts. The potential of using AI bots for counter-speech is mentioned, requiring further investigation into feasibility and consequences.

Evaluating Long-Term Effects and Balancing Priorities: The authors from 'Hate speech regulation on social media: A contemporary challenge' emphasise the importance of evaluating the long-term effects of content moderation and counter-speech approaches. It is crucial to consider potential collateral damage and strike a balance between combating hate speech and protecting freedom of speech. Transparency from social media companies regarding content removal and making data accessible for research and public scrutiny is also highlighted as an essential aspect of effective regulation.

Therefore, regulating online hate speech necessitates careful consideration of the delicate balance between freedom of speech and curbing harmful content. While challenges exist, ongoing policy debates and close monitoring of legislative initiatives worldwide are crucial. By evaluating different strategies, such as content moderation and counter-speech, while considering potential unintended consequences, we can work towards effective regulation that addresses hate speech while upholding fundamental rights. Transparency and collaboration among stakeholders are vital in shaping a safer and more inclusive online environment.

ROLE OF EDUCATION AND AWARENESS IN COMBATING HATE SPEECH AND PROMOTING TOLERANCE

Hate speech is spreading faster and further than ever before, fuelled by the growth of social media users and the rise of populism. It is not an

isolated phenomenon but is influenced by exclusionary thinking, prejudice, anger, and fear of those who are different. These thought patterns are shaped within political, social, and cultural contexts, deeply ingrained in power structures, and reinforced by systemic discrimination. However, exposure to these conditions does not automatically turn individuals into purveyors of hate speech. Strategies to combat and reject hate speech can be taught and learned.

Education plays a vital role in addressing hate speech at its core. By uncovering and challenging prejudices and stereotypes, education enables learners and educators to recognize and unpack biases. It also raises awareness of the harmful impact and consequences of hate speech, fostering the necessary skills to identify and reject hateful discourses and manipulative techniques. Critical thinking and media and information literacy are particularly valuable in this regard (UNESCO, 2023).

To effectively mitigate hate speech, a proactive approach is required. Mere reactive responses are insufficient. It is essential to create a social climate that does not foster hatred, promoting knowledge, attitudes, and skills that encourage open-mindedness, respect for human rights, and appreciation of diversity. This can be achieved through targeted educational interventions and policies (UNESCO, 2023).

Recognizing the danger of hatred to everyone, states have a responsibility to take effective measures against discrimination and promote values of mutual understanding, respect for human rights, and diversity within their education systems, as emphasized by the Assistant Secretary General for Human Rights Ilze Brands Kehris (2020).

It was stated that addressing the complex issue of hate speech requires a comprehensive approach that encompasses education, culture, and information. Multiperspectivity on cultural rights can foster critical thinking, analytic learning, and debate on history teaching becomes a

greater tool to emphasise on the complexity of history through a comparative and multi-perspective approach.

Education and Awareness in Schools

Early intervention, including through education, is crucial to prevent conflicts. The right to education is fundamental to societal stability and well-being. Understanding the drivers of hate speech requires analysing the underlying inequalities resulting from the unequal implementation of economic, social, and cultural rights and the marginalization of certain groups.

According to UNESCO, educational responses to hate speech include training teachers and learners on the values and practices related to being respectful global and digital citizens, strengthening social and emotional learning through pedagogical and whole-school approaches, and revising curricula and educational materials to make them culturally responsive and inclusive, identifying hate speech and promoting the right to freedom of expression.

To tackle hate speech effectively, UNESCO (2023) suggested that it is crucial to address its root causes. Educational activities that focus on historical and contemporary inequities should be incorporated into the formal curriculum. This targeted approach will help students understand and confront the underlying factors that contribute to hate speech.

Given the significant influence of media and information today, curricula should include dedicated modules on media literacy, information literacy, and digital citizenship. These curricula should be regularly updated to keep up with the evolving digital landscape and equip students with the necessary skills to navigate and critically analyse information.

Promoting critical thinking, social and emotional learning, intercultural dialogue, and global citizenship is essential to foster prosocial behavioural change and counter hate speech. Educational activities

that strengthen these skills should be included in curricula, empowering students to think critically, engage in meaningful dialogue, and promote inclusiveness and diversity.

Building resilience within education systems requires a comprehensive effort that extends beyond the school environment. This can be achieved through family and community outreach, as well as multi-stakeholder partnerships. By engaging all relevant stakeholders, we can create a strong support network that helps counter hate speech and promotes a culture of inclusivity.

Additionally, in educational settings, clear guidelines and mechanisms should be established and implemented to support individuals and groups who are targeted by hate speech. This includes the establishment of clear reporting mechanisms and norms for compliance. By doing so, we can ensure that affected individuals receive the necessary support and protection within educational environments.

Promoting Awareness Online

The responsibility to combat hate speech lies with every individual. It is essential for people worldwide to stand against hate, advocate for human rights, protect faith-based minorities, condemn intolerance and hate speech, and support the development and dissemination of teaching materials that foster respect for pluralism and diversity in all aspects of life.

As per the article 'Online hate speech: Education as prevention' (2020), it is suggested that the most effective long-term measures for combating hate speech are those that target culture, specifically education, information, and communication. The digital native generation, with limited face-to-face interactions, may experience a wide range of emotions but lacks the capacity to recognize and manage the emotions of others. Emotional illiteracy contributes to the promotion of hate speech online, as media content can alter individuals' emotional

states. This lack of emotional literacy is characterized by a lack of self-awareness and an inability to relate to the emotions of others. Communicating hate speech without direct interpersonal contact is also easier.

Vitullo (2021) explores the connection between education and tolerance towards hate speech, highlighting the role of education in navigating the internet, comprehending online content and language, and developing digital skills. Offline and online illiteracy reinforce each other, contributing to the spread of hate speech. Young people often lack the necessary skills to discern reliable sources of information, making them vulnerable to online misinformation. Exposure to certain types of content can desensitize young people to more violent language.

The Gruppo di lavoro Odio Online (2021) emphasizes the need for a comprehensive digital awareness educational program involving schools, families, companies, and the media. It suggests launching a cultural modernization program that strengthens the teaching of digital technology as part of civic education. Investing in the digital training of teachers is crucial to encourage creative use of technology and raise awareness about its opportunities and risks. Media education becomes essential in countries like Italy, where the digital divide persists, providing the necessary skills for responsible and productive online content creation. Parallel policies are needed to address responsible and critical use of technology and bridge knowledge and understanding gaps. The European Commission recognizes the importance of media education, aiming to standardize digital skills through frameworks such as DigComp 2.1.

By integrating education, information, and culture, and by promoting digital literacy and responsible online behaviour, society can effectively address the root causes of hate speech and foster a climate of tolerance, respect, and diversity.

Building Tolerance

To cultivate a climate of tolerance, the article titled 'Teaching Tolerance Reduces Crime and Violence' (1999) suggests that it is essential for individuals to assume personal responsibility and actively take steps to embrace diversity. As individuals, it becomes necessary to foster a sense of appreciation for their own cultural values while respecting and valuing the cultural values of others.

The articles also state that learning from the experiences and ideas of people from diverse backgrounds is also crucial. Individuals should include others who may look or act differently from themselves in various activities and refrain from labelling people based on their characteristics. Supporting victims of hate crimes and their families, as well as actively engaging in activities like writing letters to the editor or participating in peer conflict mediation groups, can contribute to promoting diversity. Additionally, becoming trained counsellors for victims of bias-motivated violence and learning how to effectively respond to offensive comments are important steps. By working together with others, people can continue their efforts to combat bias-violence and establish a society that embraces and celebrates diversity.

To effectively address the issue of hate speech, it is crucial to prioritise it and take tangible actions. This entails implementing concrete plans, policy frameworks, and allocating sufficient budgets to counter hate speech. Additionally, efforts to combat hate speech should be integrated into existing educational initiatives, ensuring a comprehensive approach to tackle the problem. By doing so, we can provide a holistic response to the issue.

While countering hate speech, it is important to uphold the right to freedom of expression. Strategies and measures taken to address hate speech should be mindful of this fundamental right, striking a balance between curbing hate speech and preserving freedom of expression.

Lastly, it is important to establish criteria for evaluating and assessing the effectiveness of interventions aimed at addressing hate speech. By monitoring and analysing the impact of these interventions, we can refine and improve our strategies, ensuring that our efforts are impactful and successful in combating hate speech.

Media Ethics

Media and journalism shape people's perceptions, especially regarding hate speech. How hate speech is portrayed in the media significantly impacts public opinion and attitudes toward different social groups. When media platforms allow hate speech or promote discriminatory ideologies, it normalizes and validates such behaviour for the audience. Biased reporting and sensationalism further amplify negative stereotypes and contribute to intolerance.

Even though ethical journalism aims to avoid promoting discrimination, it is argued that some journalists still engage in political propaganda for racist groups, and media can be used as tools of intolerance. In a complex news environment, journalists may unknowingly become victims of prejudice and political manipulation. Ignorance and a lack of understanding of different cultures, traditions, and beliefs often result in media stereotypes that reinforce racist attitudes and attract political extremists (White, OHCHR).

Therefore, it is crucial to adopt certain measures to combat hate speech in the media. Few suggestions by Poni Alice JameKolak (2016) include:

Promoting media ethics education: Addressing the issue of tribalized hate speech starts with acknowledging that while freedom of expression is a fundamental human right, the advent of social media has given rise to numerous platforms that facilitate the creation, packaging, and dissemination of hate speech. Education on media ethics should prioritize understanding the rights and freedoms of journalists, as well as their role in fostering peaceful societies.

Raising awareness of political, social, and cultural rights: It is crucial to raise awareness about the political, social, and cultural rights of individuals and groups, including the freedom of speech, and the responsibilities and societal consequences that accompany press freedom. Journalists should be equipped with the knowledge and skills necessary to identify hate speech and effectively counter hate speech messages.

Promoting conflict-sensitive reporting and multicultural awareness campaigns: Adopting conflict-sensitive reporting techniques can debunk the fallacy of an "us" versus "them" mentality. Journalists should receive training in conflict-sensitive reporting, while multicultural awareness campaigns should emphasize knowledge and respect for the diversity of cultures and traditions. Journalists should strive to adhere to professional standards, enabling them to write articles, produce programs, and engage with individuals without taking sides.

Regulating social media: The question of how to regulate social media without compromising press freedom often arises. Education on media laws and ethics can enhance press freedom. By understanding the legal and ethical boundaries, journalists can navigate the complexities of social media while upholding their professional responsibilities.

Encouraging reporting of hate speech-related crimes by victims and witnesses: Hate speech often goes unnoticed because many victims are unaware of where to report such incidents or fail to recognize that they have fallen victim to hate speech. Encouraging victims and witnesses to come forward and report hate speech-related crimes is crucial. Providing accessible reporting mechanisms and raising awareness about reporting avenues can help address this issue.

Combating impunity for hate crimes: Establishing monitoring and evaluation units within newsrooms can effectively tackle impunity for hate crimes. These units would be responsible for monitoring hate speech trends, compiling reports, and bringing them to the attention of

relevant institutions and civil society, thereby holding perpetrators accountable.

Hence, it is crucial to ensure responsible and ethical journalism that can combat hate speech by promoting inclusivity, challenging stereotypes, and fostering dialogue. Through accurate information, diverse perspectives, and a focus on understanding, media and journalism have the power to dismantle hate speech and foster a more tolerant society.

MACHINE LEARNING PROJECT - INVESTIGATING HATE SPEECH REPORTING: AN ANALYSIS DRIVEN BY DATA

Introduction

The surge in hate speech has emerged as a pressing concern in the digital era, given its potential to incite violence, perpetuate prejudice, and disrupt social cohesion. In line with ongoing research influenced by Simon Lindgren's book "Data Theory," this project seeks to delve into the reporting of hate speech, with a specific focus on news articles pertaining to hate speech in India. Through the scrutiny of data and patterns gleaned from these articles, our aim is to develop a deeper comprehension of the dynamics surrounding hate speech within the Indian context.

Background

Previous research conducted within the CDPP (Centre for Development Policy and Practice) working paper delved into the realm of internet regulation, examining the classification of countries based on the framework introduced by Ronald Deibert. Building on this foundation, this project advances to explore the data generated on hate speech, investigating how it is reported and documented in India. In doing so, we aspire to shed light on the discussion surrounding hate speech and its consequences for societal welfare.

Objective

The principal goal of this project is to gain insights into the reporting of hate speech through the application of data-driven analytical methods. Specifically, we will investigate the patterns, occurrences, and key characteristics evident in news articles concerning hate speech in India. By extracting valuable insights from the available dataset, our aim is to contribute to a more profound understanding of the factors influencing reporting and its impact on society.

Methodology

To acquire a comprehensive grasp of hate speech reporting and its analysis, we will employ the Actor-Network Theory (ANT) framework. ANT is a theory that offers a distinct perspective by considering both human and non-human entities as influential agents within a social context, and discerning how these entities are interconnected. In this project, we will apply ANT to pinpoint the various entities involved in hate speech reporting, encompassing news outlets, journalists, social media platforms, and governmental bodies. By mapping out these entities and their interactions, we can construct a social network that encapsulates the intricate dynamics surrounding hate speech in India.

Furthermore, as part of the broader field of Computational Social Sciences, we will make use of machine learning modelling techniques to analyse the hate speech data. Python, as a versatile programming language replete with rich libraries and frameworks, will be our primary tool for implementing these machine learning algorithms.

Employing machine learning models will empower us to carry out various tasks, including sentiment analysis, topic classification, and named entity recognition. Sentiment analysis aids us in gauging the emotional tone and polarity of hate speech articles, granting us insight into the overall sentiment conveyed. Techniques for topic classification assist in categorising articles into pertinent themes, shedding light on the fundamental subjects addressed in hate speech reporting. Lastly,

named entity recognition supports us in identifying and extracting significant entities, such as individuals, organisations, or locations, mentioned within the articles.

By employing these methods, we can process extensive volumes of hate speech data more efficiently and effectively. These models will furnish us with invaluable insights, allowing us to uncover patterns, relationships, and trends within the dataset. Moreover, through the utilisation of Python libraries such as scikit-learn and the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK), we can implement a range of machine learning algorithms to extract meaningful information from the hate speech corpus.

By embracing Actor-Network Theory, we identify pertinent entities and construct a social network. By utilising machine learning models for data analysis, we can achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the intricate dynamics and socio-technical aspects surrounding the issue. These interdisciplinary approaches enable us to explore the intersection of social sciences, data analysis, and technology, providing valuable insights into the mechanisms behind hate speech and informing future interventions and policy development.

Phases of the Project

Phase 1: Data Collection and Preprocessing

We will utilise our access to a substantial body of training data through the language model employed by ChatGPT. This corpus encompasses a diverse range of texts, including news articles, blogs, social media posts, and more. Using this, we will identify pertinent data specifically related to reports of hate speech in India.

Phase 2: Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA)

Once the data has been collected and preprocessed, we will conduct thorough exploratory data analysis. This analysis will encompass techniques such as statistical analysis, data visualisation, and natural

language processing (NLP) methods to delve into patterns, trends, and significant features within the data.

By scrutinising variables such as news sources, publication dates, and authorship, our objective is to gain insights into the coverage of hate speech in the country.

Phase 3: Topic Modelling and Theme Extraction

In the ultimate phase, we will apply advanced topic modelling techniques, including Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), to uncover underlying themes within the available data. Through the application of these algorithms, we aim to unearth latent topics and explore the prevailing themes that emerge from the dataset. This analysis will assist us in understanding the varied contexts and narratives present in hate speech reporting.

Detailing the Phases and the Code Used

Details of Phase 1

The data retrieval process centres on extracting headlines and article URLs from Google News search results related to the specified keywords. Here's a breakdown of the steps involved:

1. Setting up the Environment and Importing Libraries:

The code commences by importing the requisite libraries, encompassing Selenium, BeautifulSoup, and pandas, which are employed for web scraping and data manipulation.

2. Defining Custom Parameters:

Custom parameters are outlined to specify the keywords to search for and the number of pages to scrape. In this code, the `key_words` list encompasses the keywords to search, and the `_pages` variable represents the range of pages to scrape.

3. Creating the DataFrame:

The `create_df()` function is defined to manage the scraping process. It initiates a loop over the provided keywords and

establishes the Chrome web driver for Selenium. It also configures the download directory and opens the Google search page.

4. Scraping Headlines:

Within the loop, the code interacts with the Google search page to extract the headlines, URLs, and publication dates. It utilises CSS selectors to pinpoint the specific elements containing this information. The headlines are extracted using the `headline_text` CSS selector, URLs using the `headline_url` selector, and publication dates using the `headline_date` selector.

5. Storing Data in DataFrame:

The extracted headlines, URLs, and publication dates are stored in separate lists (`_headline`, `_url`, `_date`). After scraping all the pages, these lists are used to create a new DataFrame called `xyz`. The DataFrame contains columns for the attributes: `headline_date`, `key_word`, `headline_text`, and `headline_url`.

6. Saving Data to a CSV File:

The `xyz` DataFrame is saved as a CSV file named `save_file.csv` using the `to_csv()` function.

7. Closing the Web Driver:

The web driver is closed to free up system resources using the `driver.close()` function.

Loading the Scraped Data:

Upon completing the scraping process, the code loads the saved CSV file (`save_file.csv`) into a new DataFrame called `df_headings` using the `read_csv()` function.

This phase allows for the accumulation of a dataset of hate speech articles from a variety of sources, which can subsequently be used for further analysis and exploration.

Details of Phase 2

The scraper has been activated, and the time period was set to the latest three months. The results of the first two Google search pages have been scraped and stored in a separate Excel sheet. Some of the analyses based on the collected data are outlined below.

Table 1 - The top websites that reported the hate speech (table has been created by the author as an outcome of this project)

Sl. No.	Website	Count of articles
1	cjp.org.in	1
2	english.jagran.com	1
3	hindupost.in	1
4	inshorts.com	1
5	sabrangindia.in	1
6	scroll.in	1
7	theprint.in	1
8	thewire.in	1
9	www.espn.in	1
10	indianexpress.com	2
11	www.indiatoday.in	2
12	www.opindia.com	2
13	www.hindustantimes.com	5

Based on the aforementioned findings, it can be deduced that the Hindustan Times stands out as the foremost media outlet in terms of reporting hate speech. One plausible explanation could be their inclination towards covering more conservative topics. Conversely, it could also indicate a commendable openness and impartiality in addressing hate speech concerns in India. A comprehensive analysis pertaining to the latter assertions can be conducted once Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) is employed on the collection of articles disseminated by Hindustan Times. This would allow for a more nuanced examination of the overarching theme guiding their reporting on hate speech.

Figure 1 - Trend of hate Crime publications

Trend of Hate crime as per the dates

This is an example to showcase what can be found by data visualization. The trend line can be extracted for an entire year to see where the spikes and dips are matching with the other major occurrences. For example, the above trend line shows that in the past three months, June has more hate speech/hate crime articles published. There is no other data that can be used to correlate why such spike has occurred. More data would provide deeper analysis.

Figure 2 - Trend of Hate Crime Publications according to the days

Trend of the hate crime reportage as per the day

The figure 2 shows that the hate crime reportage is high during the weekends. From figure 1, the highest number of articles published was on 24 June 2023, which is Saturday. From the figure 2, the highest number of articles published is on Saturday. The second highest number of publications are found to be on Tuesdays. What does this trend say? Saturdays are perhaps the free time where people engage with their newspapers and online news, so more important stories are relayed. Not making a spurious correlation, this Saturday trend might be a general newspaper story publication trend. However, these insights from the project data gives more room for thinking.

Named Entity Recognition (NER)

Named Entity Recognition (NER) is a natural language processing technique used in the project to identify and classify named entities within textual data. It is particularly useful in identifying key actors, organizations and locations mentioned in texts, allowing for comprehensive analysis and identification of trends, patterns and relationships. It helps in gaining insights into the social, economic and cultural implications of digital technologies by recognizing and categorizing important bodies within the text corpus.

Researchers and analysts can gain insights into the individuals or groups targeted by hate speech, the locations or platforms where hate speech proliferates and the relationships between hate speech and various societal factors. Such detailed analysis allows for the development of more effective strategies and interventions to combat hate speech and promote a more inclusive and respectful digital environment.

We identified the top 25 entities that are mentioned. The number of entities considered for the trend line are limited to the frequency of 5. If the entity is repeated 5 or more times, the entity is presented in the graph.

Figure 3 - Identification of top entities within the scraped text

Top entities and their frequency

From the figure above, it is clear that India is repeated highest number of times. However, India can be mentioned as the search was narrowed down to its region and it is natural to mention India as a location. But the next highest mentioned word is Canada, which is unexpected. Perhaps, the recent news reportage is more regarding the Khalistan related groups in Canada.

Table 2 - Top 10 entities mentioned in the data extracted

Sl. No.	Entity	Count
1	India	33
2	Canada	15
3	FIR	12
4	GB	12
5	Hindu	12
6	Two	11
7	Indian	11
8	Hindus	9
9	BJP	9
10	Muslim	8

The top 10 entities that are mentioned in the text scrapped shows Hindu, Muslim, BJP. This might indicate that the hate crime is surrounded around Hindu – Muslim communal differences. There are no other minority or castes mentioned in the top 30 entities. Each article can be further analysed to find actual causes and detailed patterns.

Table 3 - Entity label counts as per the scrapped data

Sl. No.	Entity Label	Entity definition	Count
1	ORG	Companies, agencies, Institutions etc	129
2	GPE	Countries, cities, states	127
3	PERSON	People, including fictional	114
4	DATE	Absolute or relative dates or periods	100
5	NORP	Nationalities or religious or political groups	97
6	PRODUCT	Objects, vehicles, foods, etc. (Not services.)	91
7	WORK_OF_ART	Titles of books, songs, etc	12
8	LOC	Non-GPE locations, mountain ranges, bodies of water	11
9	CARDINAL	numerals	11
10	FAC	Buildings, airports, highways, bridges, etc	9
11	TIME	Times smaller than a day.	6
12	LAW	Named documents made into laws	6
13	ORDINAL	first, "second", etc	4
14	PERCENT	Percentage, including "%"	4
15	EVENT	Named hurricanes, battles, wars, sports events, etc	2
16	MONEY	Monetary values, including unit	2

Table 3 shows the total count of the entity labels. Organizations and persons are found to be mentioned many times. This encourages to look into which organization and persons are named most.

Details of Phase 3

In the Phase 3 of the study, Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) will be conducted. LDA is a topic modeling technique used to uncover latent topics within a collection of documents. It is a probabilistic model that represents documents as mixtures of topics, where each topic is characterized by a distribution of words.

By applying LDA to the dataset, insights can be gained in the following areas:

Topic Discovery: LDA helps in uncovering hidden themes or topics present in the collection of documents. It automatically identifies topics based on the distribution of words across the documents.

Document Clustering: LDA can group similar documents together based on the topics they contain. This clustering of documents provides insights into the underlying structure and relationships within the dataset.

Feature Extraction: LDA allows for the extraction of the most important words or features associated with each topic. This facilitates summarizing and understanding the content of the documents.

In Phase 3 the analysis of the resulting topics and their distributions will contribute to a deeper understanding of the key themes, patterns and relationships within the data. The outcomes of the LDA analysis will inform the research objectives and conclusions of the study.

PROJECT SUMMARY

The Machine Learning endeavour centred on delving into hate speech reporting in India through a data-informed analysis. Through processes such as data acquisition, preliminary data examination, subject

modelling, and the identification of key entities, the project sought to obtain a deeper comprehension of the trends, frequencies, and critical attributes within news articles concerning hate speech.

The analysis uncovered several significant revelations. Hindustan Times emerged as a leading source in reporting on hate speech, identified amongst the top media channels. The scrutiny of hate crime publications displayed notable upswings in June, whilst a daily breakdown highlighted heightened reportage during weekends. The application of Named Entity Recognition identified India as the most frequently referenced entity, followed by Canada, signifying a potential focus on Hindu-Muslim communal tensions. The entity categorisation analysis disclosed frequent mentions of organisations and individuals.

In the subsequent project phase, Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) was implemented for topic modelling, revealing underlying themes within hate speech reporting. This yielded a more profound insight into the prevailing subjects and storylines encapsulated in hate speech articles.

In summary, this project represents a significant contribution to the comprehensive analysis of hate speech reporting in India, amalgamating computational social sciences, machine learning methodologies, and data-driven discernments. The findings derived from this project hold the potential to guide future interventions and policy formulation, thereby fostering a more secure online milieu through a consideration of the analysed hate speech reports and their societal repercussions.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have seen that the history of hate speech is a complex and troubling one, with examples found throughout different cultures and time periods. Hate speech has been used to justify discrimination, violence, and even genocide against marginalized groups which disproportionately affects vulnerable communities, causing

psychological and physical harm that can lead to fear, humiliation, silencing, and the perpetuation of negative stereotypes.

In the present scenario, the spread of hate speech has been amplified by technology, particularly social media platforms, which enable the rapid dissemination of hateful content and the formation of like-minded communities. In a country like India, which has roots for its hate speech laws in the colonial era, is essential to highlight the inadequacy of the existing legal framework in addressing hate speech and underscore the need for a separate understanding of it. Regulating online hate speech poses challenges in balancing freedom of speech and curbing harmful content. Strategies such as content moderation and counter-speech campaigns have been employed, but careful consideration is required to address the potential unintended consequences. Hence, to address the issue of hate speech, education and awareness has the potential to play a vital role in combating hate speech, promoting tolerance, and fostering critical thinking, media literacy, and respect for diversity.

Additionally, analysing hate speech reporting in India using data-driven methods, particularly through Latent Dirichlet Allocation for topic modeling, provided us valuable insights into underlying themes. This contributed significantly to our understanding of hate speech reporting and can serve as a foundation for shaping future interventions and policies, ultimately fostering a safer online environment.

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